

RECENT E- HUMAN RESOURCE PRACTICES AND CHALLENGES IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

India now becomes a player in the global stage. Everyone wants to do business with us, this change has given lot of opportunities to our country to grow further but it posed lot of challenges in front of us like Indian companies gained confidence to acquire foreign giant companies and try to establish themselves very competitive than the foreign companies at the same time we have to give emphasis on the various challenges before us like the gap between people in the corporate world and those in the rural areas is becoming serious concern and the wage differentials between blue collared workers and senior managers, the candidates having good education and communication skills getting more chance in the job market than other people lesser than them, attrition levels are all time high in India for example business process outsourcing facing problems with talent retention.

Key Words: GOLD, MAD, EHRM, HRIS.

INTRODUCTION

Companies that desire to maintain a competitive edge, both now and in the future require human force well equipped to face the ever increasing pace of technological changes and techniques. This is the accountability of the human force manager to properly train the work force to accomplish the competitive advantages of business in the 21st century. HRM managers have moved from handling simple personal issues to making a strategic implementation through supporting the long term strategies with the necessary employee qualifications and developing the cultural and technical capabilities required for the strategies of the organization. In recent years there has been considerable debate regarding human resource management (Bal, 2011, p-2). One has to rise the question here what should be the priorities for human resource in future? Though we believe that human plays a vital role in an organization but due to rapidly transforming business landscape, globalization, changing nature of consumer taste and habits, a new techniques of production, HR managers are facing a variety of issues and challenges like retention of the employees, multicultural work force, retrenchment of the employees. Armstrong (2004) defined Human Resource Management (HRM) as the function within an organization that focuses on recruitment of management of, and providing direction for the people who work in the organization. Human resource manager will have to build or develop a frame work that

allows flexibility to develop a workforce for tomorrow (Andries du plessis, 2008, p-167). The primary focus of the paper is to explore HR issues and challenges and to provide practical solutions.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The world federation of personnel management association (WFPMA, 2009) survey pointed out the most important top ten HR challenges are leadership development, organizational effectiveness, change management, compensation, health and safety, staff retention, learning and development, succession planning, staffing: recruitment and skill labour. In the view point of Decenzo and Robins (2001) the most important challenges of HRM, are technology, E commerce, and work force diversity, and globalization, ethical consideration of the organization which may directly or indirectly affect the organization competitive advantages, especially with technological advancement the affect on recruitment, training and development and job performance with great extent can be study in organization.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

Through this research an endeavor has been made to identify the challenges involved in achieving administrative/service excellence by companies through E-HRM and also the challenges of moving towards performance excellence. By understanding and overcoming these challenges, companies can be successful in achieving the primary objective of any E-

HRM venture i.e. to diminish costs of HR transactions, condense time value and make resources easily available for utilization.

The objectives of this research are:

- To identify the underlying factors and pre- requisites for the success of an e-HRM venture.
- To identify the challenges associated with the implementation and maintenance of e-HRM systems.
- To offer recommendations and suggestions for enhancing the effectiveness of e-HRM systems.

Factors affecting the role of HRM

Globalization

Greengard (1995) defined globalization as the system of interaction among the countries of the world in order to develop the global economy. Globalization refers to the amalgamation of economics and societies around the world which means that world trade and financial markets are becoming more integrated. Growing internationalization of business has its impact on HRM in terms of problems of unfamiliar laws, languages, practices, competitions, attitudes, management styles, work ethics etc (Srivastava & Agarwal). Globalization has an effect on employment patterns worldwide. It has contributed to a great deal of outsourcing which is one of the greatest organizational and industry structure shifts that change the way business operates (Drucker, 1998). Globalization is also seen as changing organizational structures where expenses can move up or down as the business climate dictates (Garr, 2001). As a result HR managers have to confront with more heterogeneous functions and more involvement in employee's personal life.

Technological advances

Technological advances have a significant impact on HR business practices. Due to the advancements in the technology there has been a drastic change in the approach to the various projects and the scenarios that guide to the organizational regulations.

Firstly, the need of skilled personals is mentionable. In order to survive in a competitive environment the organization definitely in need of the skilled personals in substantial number to handle the situations and technical equipments. In an organization there are "hot" sectors which require a high of technical experts like telecommunications, hospitality, retailing, banking,

insurance, bio-technology etc. Next head which is worth mentioning is the downsizing. New technologies have decimated many lower-end jobs with frustrating regularity. The increased automation also has reduced the employee head counts everywhere. The pressure of remaining cost-effective in every aspect has also compelled many a firm to go lean, and thereby cutting down extra fat at each and every managerial level (Anurag, 2011). Managing the expectations of knowledge workers is also going to be a major area of concern for all HR managers in the years ahead.

Other aspect is telecommuting where the employees started to work remotely from a place other than their primary office. Telecommuting became a popular alternative to avoid the daily commute where the employees use phones and internet to transmit their office works.

This has been a powerful cost effective tool in the sense that companies have been successful in increasing their applicant pool through this mode and staffs also may live far away from cities and gain considerably due to savings in rents, transportation, etc.

The biggest issue due to technological advancement is adaptability, with companies looking at tools which can integrate with the internet, while other issues of concern include data privacy, security and business continuity/disaster recovery.

Workforce Diversity

Diversity by definition for the business world means having a workforce that represents many different viewpoints, backgrounds and cultures. Diversity affects all areas of organizations from recruitment to compensation, to the affect it has on the corporate culture, morale and competitiveness. Diversity in the workplace is an increasingly topical theme in management. Diversity within HRM, termed as workforce diversity, is a multifaceted phenomenon that can be defined as any visible or invisible difference between organisational members. Diversity can be labelled into two distinct aspects: observable differences (e.g. nationality, age) and underlying differences (e.g. values, sexual orientation). Workforce diversity becomes a particular issue in HRM as it has legal, moral and business implications for an organization.

There are a number of ways in which people respond to diversity. Behavioural and emotional reactions to diversity are explained largely by three theories: the similarity attraction paradigm, social identity theory and social categorisation theory (Pearson, 1995). Workplace diversity has its positive effects (e.g. innovation, flexibility) as well as negative effects (e.g. high turnover, decreased job satisfaction). However, diversity management can help mitigate the adverse effects of diversity and capitalise on the positive effects.

With the fusion of talents of diverse cultural backgrounds, genders, ages and lifestyles, an organization can respond to business prospects more vividly and creatively, especially in the

global arena, which must be one of the main organizational goals to be attained. The risks of losing talents to competitors occur when an organizational environment does not support diversity. This is especially factual for a multinational company (MNCs) who have ventures on a global scale and employ people with varies ethical and cultural backgrounds. Thus, a HR manager needs to be mindful and may employ a Think Global, Act Local approach in most circumstances.

Changes in political and legal environment:

If there are Changes in political and legal environment, then almost all aspects of HRM will be affected by the legal and regulatory environment. The key drivers of a political climate include the extent of external regulations, nature of work contracts, various labour legislations and case laws etc. Such factors remain ever changing, and as such, the political atmosphere of human resource management remains in a constant change of flux. It is the duty of human resource and industrial relations executives to anticipate the changes and fully examine the implication, of these changes and brings about necessary adjustment within the organization so that they can face any changes without any breakdown in its normal functioning (Srivastava & Agarwal, p-47)

Changes in the Economic Environment:

In an economic situation companies suffer both internal and external pressures. The external competitive pressure stemming from the economic crisis produces a drop in demand and an increase in unemployment, which in turn affects the global competition in the market. On the other hand the internal management of the company focuses on efficiency. This leads to pressure to reduce costs and fringe expenditure, as well as to the need to justify the need for each and the total amount of all expenditure to be incurred. High unemployment and layoffs are clearly HRM and managerial issues. Without a doubt, these matters influence the strategic HR function. In an inflationary economy, the resources tend to become scarce and the costs of machine, materials and labour multiply. These push up the capital and running costs.

Ethics

While considering the challenges of human resources there is a need to discuss about ethics. The discussion about ethics happened during mid 2000s when several companies were found to have engaged in gross unethical and illegal conduct, resulting in the loss of billions of dollars from shareholders. Companies are seeing the value of implementing ethics codes within the business. Many human resource departments have the responsibility of designing codes of ethics and developing policies for ethical decision making. According to Steve Miranda, chief human resources officer for the Society for Human Resource Management (SHRM), "[the presence of

an ethics officer] provides a high-level individual with positional authority who can ensure that policies, practices, and guidelines are effectively communicated across the organization"(McGraw, 2011). Developing policies, monitoring behaviour, and informing people of ethics are necessary to ensure a fair and legal business.

In the present era most of the organizations are competing globally for their best reputation, by keeping in view the above issues and challenges the HR managers are responsible to train all the young workers, to provide them best rewards as a result they will show their commitment and loyalty.

- Technology has changed each and everything with great extent, the methods of production, the process of recruitment, the training techniques, new equipment and technology should be introduced and purchase by the organization and training should be provided to young and educated workers.

- To cope up with the issue of Globalization HR manager should adopt the concept of Globalize Human Resource Management (GHRM) where it prepares the skill people or manager worldwide. This way the trend of globalization can be minimized with some extent.

- Human resource manager should develop such a HR system which consistent with other organization elements such as organization strategies, goals and organization style, and organization planning.

- Regarding the debate on work force diversity, the HR manager accountable to make such a broad strategies which help to adjust employees in global organization, HR must increase the ability to compete in the international market.

- Organization culture is also another important element which must be consider by the HR manager, the culture must be like to shape their behavior and beliefs to observe to what is imperative.

- To provide more and more talent people into the organization the HR manager must re-decide and re-arrange the staffing functions, for recruitment selection, training and transfer, promotion, dismissals, placement, demotion and layoffs of the employees separate strategies should be developed and implemented.

FOUR CRITICAL DIMENSIONS OF BEST PRACTICES

Attract and Access

Attracting and retaining talent is becoming a big problem for every organization, they are following every trick and strategy to recruit and retain the employees.

Develop and Grow

Nowadays organizations try to recognize the aspirations of employees and focus on their growth and development. India provides job rotation opportunities to high – performing employees from operations division. This gives them broader understanding of the business.

Engage and Align

Employee engagement has retained the focus of organizational leadership and many companies keep launching new practices to woo employees. They are using innovative practices like “Loyalty Interview”- to find out what is it that makes its employees stay on, the feedback from loyal employees often reflects on the leadership style and is seen to work as a great motivation.

Transition

Movement of talent within the organization and outside of the organization sends strong signals to the employees about the organization’s care and concern. Right from the induction, which is often the first impression the employees carries, to the exit interview, the sensitivity displayed by the organization has a lasting impact on all employees.

INNOVATIVE PRACTICES IN HR AREAS

- I. Recruitment and selection
- ii .Learning and development
- iii. Rewards and recognition
- iv. Career planning
- v. Compensation and benefits
- vi. Performance management
- vii. Leadership and development
- viii. Organization structure

RECRUITMENT AND SELECTION

1. Google

- (i) Diversity among employees: Ex – army man to former school teacher in the workforce.
- (ii) For recruitment they expect the person has to be comfortable with technology and be optimistic about the future. “Like someone who you would find interesting on a long train journey”. The company’s recruitment process ensures that it gets the people edge it needs. There is a battery of wiring tests, interviews are rigorous, not in the sense of being a stress interview,

but interviewers try and go deep into what makes the candidate tick. Then the detailed feedback on the candidate is given to an independent team in charge of hiring. The company's credo is to hire someone who is better than you.

2. Employee referrals by employees which comprises 50% of all hiring at SAP Labs India, Bangalore.

3. Non – standard pool of talent: housewives with a gap in career

4. "Bar Raisers":

The HR department has organized an elite group of 34 employees – who have veto power in an recruitment decision, if a Bar member feels a potential recruit does not match upto the company's standards.

5. Short stories:

The Company compiled 52 short stories, one for each week, the company used to introduce new recruits. The stories talk about its history and evolution, technology and people who made a difference.

6. The company goes beyond its employees and connects with their support group: the family, when an employee joins, his parents or spouse get a welcome letter.

LEARNING AND DEVELOPMENT

SME's (Subject Matter Experts):

HR team identifies the internal subject matter experts to give training to the employees
Sending employees for higher studies

E -Welcome

When employees join the company, they have to interact with functionaries in other regions who assume that the new person in knows the internal systems. Often the new employee is unfamiliar with the systems and is at sea. The E-Welcome gateway lists certain universal systems of the company and helps them get familiar with such things. A stand – out feature is that if this checklist remains incomplete it sends an automatic notice to the manager responsible for the employee.

Company follows a training policy to have seven days of training every year is mandatory for all employees, even this chairman and the directors.

GOLD (Godrej Organization for Learning and Development):

Web-based learning tied up with UK – based NetG to distribute e- learning modules among the workforce. The company gives equal importance to soft skill training. “ Out of box thinking is more important “, the sponsored the Edward De Bono certification of lateral thinking for two of its managerial employees, so they could teach in – house. This learning creates a leadership pipeline.

REWARDS AND RECOGNITION

1. MAD (Mutual Admiration):

Is an event where every employee is given green cardboard leaves on which they scribble messages of appreciation and pin them onto the MAD tree in the cafeteria. The leaves are a way of reaching out to colleagues and teams who have mattered. And at the end of the week, the foliage gets thick. Surely, the employees like being around each other.

2. Smart Work and Smart Reward:

It directed towards improving employees productivity. It rewards those who complete tasks in fewer working hours than stipulated.” The reward process is well defined and transparent. It has helped in ensuring better work – life balance.

3. Promotion within

CAREER PLANNING

1. Career Success Centre:

An online portal and a one – stop shop for all career related resources. The portal helps employees plan and develop their careers according to business needs.

COMPENSATION AND BENEFITS

1. Paternity leave

2. Extra three months maternity leave at half the salary leave

3. No attendance monitoring

4. unlimited sick leave

5. equal privileges for employees across levels: employees at all levels travel in the same class, stay in similar hotels, work out of standard cubicles, log in their own leave.

PERFORMANCE MANAGEMENT

1. 360 degree feedback system
2. "Performance Task Force": A cross functional team constitutes 20 members and this force keeps track of what needs to be plugged, and what seems to be working. It goes back to HR every six months to deliver feedback.

LEADERSHIP AND DEVELOPMENT

1. Food for thought:
Inviting employees in groups to chat with Managing director over lunch in an informal environment on various issues and topics.
2. Succession planning
3. Employee empowerment
4. Reach out:
An initiative to keep a direct link of communication to its employees, the president of the company meets the employees.

ORGANIZATION STRUCTURE

1. Flexi and Part – time
2. The companies allow the employees to shift jobs if they wish to, across its different functions.
3. Skits: The companies are asking the employees to devise skits to dramatize its values, design screen savers and even create mascots themed on the values, they would much rather hunker down and design some more.
4. The company created new position called "Employee Engagement Manager": the major task of the manager is to energize the workplace with fun – filled events and effective communication.
5. "People Champions": Every project team has one facilitator from the HR department. The people champion takes care of any administrative need a project might have, leaving the project members free to concentrate on their work.
6. Orientation along with parents: The Company invites the parents of new recruits for orientation, its good for the parents to know the kind of organization their children work for, this insight came from campus recruitment, where parents would stay with their children right till results were parents would stay with their children right till results were announced.
7. "People Movement Management Review Committee": it ensures talented employees were retained by reassigning them to other groups. The company also hired consultants to assist those who were asked to leave to find jobs in other organizations.

Conclusions

In the present competitive world, the companies are facing lot of skill shortage, talent crunch and attrition those reached historically height ever, that made the companies feel the internal customer also more important equally with external customers, so every company try to devise innovative HR practices to attract best talent , giving them nice environment to work with, that enables the company to retain talents, the above said practices are conceived and implemented and found successful by the leading companies in India. It is found that convergence of practices of different companies in different HR areas, if any company wants to apply those practices that will benefit for the company to become more competitive in the global market.

As we have discussed the dominant issues and challenges which are facing by HR mangers and organization. The foremost work by the HR is to develop sound organizational structure with strong interpersonal skill to employees. Training employees by familiarize them with the concept of globalize human resource management to perform better in the global organization context. All these issues and challenges like, work force diversity, leadership development. organizational effectiveness, Globalization, E- Commerce, etc, can be best manage by HR manager where they have to adopt a HR practice which encourages rigid recruitment and selection policy, division of jobs, empowerment, encouraging diversity in the workplace, training and development of the work force, fostering innovation, proper assigning of duties and responsibilities, managing knowledge. By enthusiastically following all the above aspects the value of human resource can be improved, organization efficiency can be enhanced, and the organization will sustain to survive.

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